

Effects of Computer – Assisted Instruction on Retention of Junior Secondary School Students in Social Studies in Niger State, Nigeria

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ABSTRACT

This study determined the effects of computer assisted instructional mode on retention level of Junior Secondary School students in social studies. The study adopted the pretest – posttest experimental – control group design. A sample of two hundred and forty (240) students was drawn from six Junior Secondary Schools in seven educational zones of Niger State. Two research questions were raised and two null hypotheses were tested at 0.05 alpha level. Data were collected using the developed CAIMOSOS and analyzed. The result of hypothesis one indicated that there was statistically significant difference between the retention of students taught Social Studies using Computer Assisted Instructional mode and those taught with conventional lecture method. While hypothesis two showed that there was no significant difference in the retention scores of male and female students taught Social Studies with Computer- Assisted Instructional mode. It was therefore recommended that CAIMOSOS was found to improve retention of students in social studies, therefore, teachers should familiarize themselves with the use of the package through government sponsored workshops and seminars so that they can use it to improve the retention of their students in social studies.

Keywords: Computer assisted instructional mode, Social Studies Retention Test (SOSRET), Retention, Junior Secondary School.

INTRODUCTION

Retention is the ability of students to recall what they learnt in the classroom during learning. Dennis (2008) and Mezieobi (2016) opined that audio visual aids such as computer related devices are indispensable and that without it, no effective learning can take place. He observed that what a child hears and sees at the time of teaching is better registered and can easily be remembered when needed. The use of computer instructional mode as an interactive instructional strategy, to present materials, track learning and direct the learners and the teachers to use additional materials that they may need in the teaching and learning processes. This is because the use of computer instructional mode provides

various audio- and video packages, it makes learning and teaching interesting and self-paced, the students could learn at their own time and pace (Udofia, Ekpo, & Akpan. 2012; Cyril, 2016).

Several studies revealed positive significant effect of computer on instructional delivery and students' academic performance. For example, studies by Gultekin (2011); Oluwatayo and Fatoba (2010) and Cyril, (2016) indicated that computer instructional package aids retention in learning by appealing to human senses simultaneously than traditional teaching method. Study by Abdu-Raheem (2012) also revealed that there was no significant difference between the retention means scores of male and female students in the experimental and control groups. Igboko and

Ibeneme (2000) found that there was no significant difference between the mean scores of students taught by the constructivist method and those taught by the traditional method in the retention test. On the other hand, Adeosun (2002) found that girls have better retention than boys in his research carried out on effect of multi-media packages on students' achievement and retention in Social Studies.

However, reflective inquiry, problem solving and decision making have been regarded as essential skills for the development of contemporary Social Studies education (Berson, 1996; Rice & Wilson, 1999). Retention is important in Social Studies performance in Nigeria. It has been reported that retention of students is affected by several factors which influences performance. Consequently, Computer Assisted Instruction (CAI) has been shown to play key role in enhancing ability on performance (Kara, 2008; Akpan, & Aminikpo, 2017).

Furthermore, the researcher has observed that, many studies carried out in Social Studies were not focused on the aspects of the concepts covered by this research, because many focused on achievement and ability, this implied that there is yet to be any single research that has examined the effectiveness of CAI on retention level of students in Social Studies concepts covered in this research. This is why this particular study is unique, considering the level of Junior Secondary School Education (that is, JSS III) that was involved, most especially in this part of Nigeria (Niger State).

It is important to note that despite all efforts put in place to teach Social Studies among junior secondary schools, performance of students has been unsatisfactory over the years. (Mezieobi,*et.al.*, 2017) pointed out that there were challenges of poor learning

environment, lack of adequate instructional materials, over-crowding in a classroom and poor method of teaching, etc. Government's lip-service on funding and in making provision of teaching materials; absence of well-equipped computer centers for use; and resistance by some teachers to adopt modern teaching techniques were also contributing factors to poor performance of students in the subject. Modern technology in education should equip teachers and learner with skills that enable them use such technologies (Laleye, 2019).

Lasisi, Alabi and Salaudeen (2016) posited that the teacher provides illustrative materials for students' self-study, and therefore, asks questions that elicit critical thinking and knowledge construction in this learning approach. The underlying principle is that when students' searches, discovers, and construct knowledge themselves under the guidance of the teacher, it encourages independent learning, creativity, critical thinking, problem solving, and active participation (Lasisi, Alabi, & Salaudeen, 2016).

Records of poor performances in Social Studies at the National Examination Council JSS examinations in Niger State show the percentage credit levels (A1- C6) rates at 31.10% in 2015, 34.68% in 2016, 37.73% in 2017, 40.67% in 2018 and 46.28% in 2019 respectively (NECO Result). All these are evidences of poor retention and it was reported that students of different ability levels vary in achievement and most of the students at high retention level were those that passed at credit level as reported by researchers. It was on this basis that this research investigated the effectiveness of computer-assisted instructional modes on retention level of students of JSS Social Studies in Niger State.

Objectives of the Study

1. To determine whether Junior Secondary School students taught Social Studies by

means of the computer-assisted instructional mode have higher retention than those students that were taught by conventional lecture method.

2. To determine the retention level of male and female students taught Social Studies by means of the computer-assisted instructional mode and those taught by conventional lecture method.

Hypotheses

1. There is no significant difference in retention among Junior Secondary School students taught Social Studies with Computer Assisted Instructional mode and those taught with conventional lecture method.
2. There is no significant difference in the retention level between male and female students taught Social Studies with Computer Assisted Instructional mode.

METHODOLOGY

The study adopted the pretest – posttest experimental – control group design. The sampling techniques of two hundred and forty (240) students were drawn from six Junior Secondary Schools in seven educational zones of Niger State. The participants (Students) were assigned to experimental and control groups by random sampling method through what is called ‘draw from the hat’ technique. This technique involves squeezing marked and unmarked pieces of papers put in a hat for the students

RESULTS

Hypothesis 1

There is no significant difference between the retention level of learning of students’ taught Social Studies using Computer Assisted Instructional mode and those taught with conventional lecture Method.

to pick. After picking, the students opened and joined the respective group, those that were marked as experimental group and those unmarked as control group.

For the purpose of this research, two types of treatment instruments were designed and used for data collection. Computer Assisted Instructional Mode on Social Studies (CAIMOSOS) was the first treatment instrument used for the experimental group, designed and produced by the researcher with the help of a computer programmer. It was structured to teach the different concepts in social studies. Social Studies Retention Test (Delayed Test) (SOSRET) was the second instrument and the content of SOSRET was the same as the SOSAT, because it was reshuffled to give the SOSRET. The reshuffled questions produced the effect of pretest which made the respondents unable to easily recognize the instrument as a familiar one from the earlier pretest and posttest. Students were divided into experimental and control groups, treatment was administered to the experimental group while the control group received no treatment. The instruments were validated. The questionnaires were administered in a span of three weeks. Analysis of Covariance (ANCOVA) was used to test the null hypotheses through Statistical Package for the Social Sciences (SPSS) at 0.05 significant levels.

Table 1: Analysis of Covariance (ANCOVA) of the Retention Mean Scores of Students’ taught Social Studies Using CAI Mode and those taught with Conventional Lecture Method

Source	Type III Sum of Squares	df	Mean Square	F	Sig.
Corrected Model	24675.857 ^a	2	12337.928	268.058	.001
Intercept	7605.095	1	7605.095	165.231	.001
Pretest	16520.853	1	16520.853	358.937	.001
Treatment	2797.571	1	2797.571	60.781	.001
Error	10908.439	237	46.027		
Total	711123.000	240			
Corrected Total	35584.296	239			

*Significant at $P < 0.05$

Table 1. Shows the ANCOVA analysis of the retention scores of experimental and control groups. The effects of treatment was produced at $P=0.001$. The main effect was significant at ($P < 0.05$). This indicates that there was a significant difference in the retention mean scores of experimental and control groups. Therefore, the Hypothesis one (H_0) that stated no significant difference

between the retention level of learning of students’ taught Social Studies using Computer Assisted Instructional mode and those taught with conventional lecture method was rejected. Since it was established that there was a significant difference between the groups, the mean gain was tabulated to locate the direction of the difference. The result is presented in Table 1.

Table 2: The retention Mean Gain Scores of Students taught with CAI and those taught with Conventional lecture Method

Group	Pretest	Posttest	Mean Gain
Experimental	42.48	58.88	16.40
Control	36.67	47.23	10.56

Table 2 revealed that the experimental group has the highest mean gain of 16.40 while the control group has the lowest mean gain of 10.56. Therefore, the significant difference is in favour of the

experimental group which was treated with Computer- Assisted Instructional mode. This can be illustrated graphically as shown in figure 1 below

Figure 1: Graphical Illustration of the Mean Gain of retention scores of students taught Social Studies with CAI and those taught with conventional lecture method (Field work, 2022)

In figure 1 the mean gain of experimental group is the blue colour line while the red

colour line is the mean gain of the control group.

Hypothesis 2

There is no significant difference in the retention level of learning between male and female students' taught Social Studies using Computer Assisted Instructional mode.

Table 3 Analysis of Covariance (ANCOVA) of the Retention Scores of Male and Female Students' taught Social Studies Using CAI Mode

Source	Type III Sum of Squares	df	Mean Square	F	Sig.
Corrected Model	15499.974 ^a	2	7749.987	128.801	.000
Intercept	2241.972	1	2241.972	37.261	.000
Pretest	15435.441	1	15435.441	256.530	.000
Gender	117.472	1	117.472	1.952	.165
Error	7039.893	117	60.170		
Total	439788.000	120			
Corrected Total	22539.867	119			

NS= not significant at 0.05

Table 2 shows the analysis of variance for the data on the achievement scores of male and female students taught Social Studies with Computer-Assisted Instructional mode. The results yielded a P-value of 0.165. This showed that the result was not significant at $P > 0.05$. This indicates that there is statistically no significant difference in the performance of male and female students taught Social Studies with Computer-Assisted Instructional mode on the retention of students. Therefore, the hypothesis two (Ho2) that stated there is no significant difference in the retention level of learning of male and female students' taught Social Studies using Computer Assisted Instructional mode was not rejected.

DISCUSSION OF FINDINGS

The results showed that there was a significant difference in the retention of students' taught Social Studies using Computer-Assisted Instructional mode and those taught with conventional lecture method. The significant difference is in favour of the experimental group which was

treated with Computer-Assisted Instructional mode. This finding was in agreement with Gultekin (2011); Oluwatayo and Fatoba (2010) and Cyril, (2016) found that Computer Instructional Package aids retention in learning by appealing to human senses simultaneously than traditional teaching method. It also corroborates Glennan and Melmed (1996), Wu and Tai, (2016) who observed that computer application in the classroom improves motivation and learning. They further explained that the more the students' five senses are engaged in the trial and presentation process, the higher the proportion of remembering.

Kara (2008) investigated the retention effect of Computer-Assisted Instruction on students' academic achievement for teaching the Force and Pressure units in Physics topics. At the end of the study, significant differences between the Science subject test scores of experimental and control groups were found in favor of experimental group. This was in accordance with the findings of

this research. Altun, Yiğit and Alev (2007), Yerizon and Subhan, (2018) found that Computer Assisted Instruction is more feasible than the traditional approach in terms of cognitive and affective behaviors. This finding has buttressed this assertion especially in terms of the cognitive behavior. Also, Nurse (2009) compared knowledge acquisition and retention, modification in clinical practice and learner satisfaction using Computer-Assisted Instruction and traditional classroom instruction in teaching positioning and pushing guidelines during the second stage of labor. The results indicated that nurses completing the module using the computer exhibited higher knowledge scores, retained more knowledge and reported greater satisfaction with CAI. This research finding has clearly supported the result of CAI utilization in the classroom (Nurse, (2009)

This is also in agreement with Olga Pilli (2008), and D. A. Udu, (2019) who reported the effects of computer software Frizbi Mathematics4on 4th grade student's where the control group consisted of 26 students where the experimental group consisted of 29 students. The groups were compared on achievement of Mathematics, retention, and attitude toward Mathematics and Computer- Assisted Learning.

There was no statistically significant difference in the retention level of learning of male and female students taught Social Studies using Computer- Assisted Instructional mode. This corroborated the findings of Abdu-Raheem (2012) also revealed that there was no significant difference between the retention means scores of male and female students in the experimental and control groups. His study confirmed that the main effect of gender on student retention in Social Studies is not significant. The male and female students exposed to the same treatment do not differ significantly in their retention means scores.

This research is contrary to Adeosun (2002) found that girls have better retention than boys in his research carried out on effect of multi-media packages on students' achievement and retention in Social Studies.

However, Abdu-Raheem (2012) believed that girls achieved and retained equally with boys because of the facts that education of the girl-child is now given better attention by the government and the society generally. This opportunity gives room for girls to use their untapped intellectual potentials effectively and erase the old stereotype that places boys above girls on academic issues. This research is also in agreement with Carter (2004) who compared the two different teaching methods based on retention rate and results indicated that no significant difference in students' retention mean scores for traditional and computer-assisted mathematics course. Igboko and Ibeneme (2000) supported the findings of this study. They showed that there was no significant difference between the mean scores of students taught by the constructivist method and those taught by the traditional method in the retention test. This showed that, the constructivist learning approach and the conventional approach are equally effective with regards to students' retention of information in Introductory Technology at the JSS level.

CONCLUSION

From this research, it is evident that there was statistically significant difference in the retention level of learning; of male and female students taught Social Studies using Computer- Assisted Instructional mode and those taught with conventional lecture methods. While there was no statistically significant difference in the retention level of learning of male and female students taught Social Studies with Computer Assisted Instructional mode respectively.

RECOMMENDATIONS

The following recommendations are made based on the findings of this research.

1. The CAIMOSOS was found to improve retention of students in social studies, therefore, teachers should familiarize themselves with the use of the package through government sponsored workshops and seminars so that they can use it to improve the retention of their students in social studies.
2. Male and Female students should use the CAIMOSOS individually in order to improve their learning retention since the package has been found to improve learning retention irrespective of gender. This is possible because the package can be readily available on CD and DVDs for individual use.

REFERENCES

- AbduRaheem, B. O. (2012). Gender differences and students' academic achievement and retention in social studies among junior secondary schools in Ekiti State, *European Journal of Educational studies*, 4(1), 154-161.
- Adeosun, O. V. (2002). *Relative effects of three multi-media packages on students' Achievement and Retention in Social Studies*. Unpublished PhD Thesis, University of Ado- Ekiti, Ado-Ekiti.
- Akpan, K.P. and Aminikp, N. R. (2017). Blended learning approach on students' academic achievement and retention: A case study of Air force Secondary school, Port- Harcourt, River State, Nigeria. *International Journal of Multi disciplinary Research and Development*, 4(12), 15-21.
- Altun, T., Yigit, N. & Alev, N. (2007). The effects of computer supported materials on student achievements and perceptions in science education. *Conference IMCL, 18 -20, April 2007*. Amman, Jordan.
- Berson, M. J. (1996). Effectiveness of computer technology in the social studies: A review of the literature. *Journal of Research on Computing in Education*, 2(4), 486-499.
- Carter, M. B. (2004). *An analysis and comparison of the effects of computer assisted instruction versus traditional lecture instruction students attitudes and achievements in a college remedial mathematics course*. Unpublished Doctoral Dissertation University of Temple, Philadelphia, USA.
- Cyril, M. U. (2016). Effects of multimedia instruction on retention and achievement of basic skills in mechanical craft practice. *International journal of Education and information technology*, 2(1), 1-7.
- Dannis, F. J. (2008). Individual difference in mental ability in learning situation. *Journal of Education Psychology*, 65 (3), 837-847.
- Fraenkel, I. R. & Wallen, N. E. (2000). *How to design and evaluate research in education* (Fifth Edition). Mcgraw-Hill Company, Inc., 1221 Avenue of the Americas, New York: USA
- Gultekin, A. (2011). *Comparing traditional and computer assisted education in the teaching of colour to 6th grade students and determination of its retention*. Department of Applied Arts, Art and Design Faculty, Gazi University, Ankara, Turkey. An Unpublished Masters' Thesis.
- Igboko, R. O. & Ibeneme, T. O. (2006). Effects of some Cognitive Constructivism Instructional Approaches on students' Achievement and Retention in the study of Introductory Technology in Nigeria. *Journal of Science Teachers Association of Nigeria*, 41(1&), 37-43.
- Kara, I. (2008). The effect on retention of computer assisted instruction in science education. *Journal of Instructional Psychology*, 35(4), 357-364.
- Laleye, A. M. (2019). Effects of a computer-programmed instructional strategy on

- basic science students' learning outcome in two instructional settings in Ondo State, Nigeria. *International Journal of Scientific Research and Management (IJSRM)*, 07(02), 869-876.
- Lasisi, N., Alabi, T. O. & Salaudeen, M. B. (2016). Comparison of the effects of guided discovery, problem solving and conventional teaching methods on retention of Secondary school Chemistry students in Minna Metropolis, Niger State. *American journal of innovative Research and Applied Science*, 2(3), 98-104.
- Mezeiobi, D. I. (2019). Computer- Aided- Instruction (CAI) as an innovative Method for Optimizing the Quality of social studies lecturers in Nigerian Tertiary Institutions for Quality Teacher Education in Nigeria.
- Nurse, R. (2009). *Computer-assisted versus traditional classroom instruction to promote change in the nursing management of the second stage of labor*. Unpublished Ph.D.Thesis, Texas Woman's University, Denton, Texas.
- Oluwatayo, J. A. & Fatoba, J. O. (2010). Effects of evaluative feedback on performance and retention of secondary school students in Biology. *International Journal of Science Education*, 2(1), 55-59.
- Pilli, O. (2008). *The effects of computer-assisted instruction on the students' achievements, attitudes and retention in the Fourth Grade Mathematics Course*. Unpublished Doctoral Dissertation University of Middle East Technical, Ankara, Turkey.
- Sambo, A. A. (2005). *Research methods in education*. Ibadan: Stirling-Horden Publishers (Nig.) Ltd.
- Udofia, A. E., Ekpo, A. O. & Akpan, E. O. (2012). instructional variable and students acquisition of employable skills in vocational education in Nigeria Technical Colleges. *Scholarly Journal of Education*, 1(2), 13-19.
- Udu, D. A. (2019). Efficacies of cooperative learning instructional approach, learning activity package, and lecture method in enhancing students' academic retention in Chemistry. *Science Education International*, 29(4), 220-227.
- Wu, T. J. & Tai, Y. N. (2016). Effects of multimedia information Technology integrated multi-sensory instruction on students' learning motivation and outcome," Eurasia. *Journal of mathematics, Science and Technology Education*, 12(4), 065-1074.
- Yerizon, A. A. P. & Subhan, M. (2018). Mathematics learning instructional development based on discovery learning for students' with intrapersonal and interpersonal intelligence (preliminary research stage). *International Electronic Journal of Mathematics Education*, 13(3), 97-101.